

Table 2. Reaction of TM 2011 to pests and diseases.
RRS, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-88.

Pest or disease	Resistance rating ^a	
	TM2011	IR50
Bacterial blight		
Coimbatore	3	5
Blast		
Aduthurai	0	4
Coimbatore	5	7
Brown spot		
Coimbatore	5	5
Sheath rot		
Aduthurai	5	3
Tungro		
Aduthurai	5	3
Coimbatore	7	5
Brown planthopper		
Ambasamudram	3	5

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

(IET10883) performed well in six of eight locations, with 10.6% higher yield than national check Akashi recording a mean grain yield of 3.5 t/ha. □

Integrated germplasm improvement— rainfed lowland

TM6012, a short-duration rainfed rice

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TM6012 is a short-duration, drought-resistant rice selection derived from C22/BJ1. It has a 115-d duration and is suitable for a season with 890-940 mm rainfall.

TM6012 was compared with PMK1 in the 1985-88 wet seasons. It averaged 2.3 t/ha; PMK1 yielded 1.8 t/ha (see table).

TM6012 has fine grain and is resistant to blast. It has field tolerance for leafhopper, gall midge, and sheath rot. □

Performance of TM6012.

Character	PMK1 (check)	TM6012
Parentage	CO 25/ADT31	C22/BJ1
Duration (d)	110-115	115-120
Plant height (cm)	71.00	90.00
Productive tillers (no./plant)	4.50	6.80
Panicle length (cm)	15.70	18.50
Filled grains (no./panicle)	63.60	72.50
Empty spikelets (no./panicle)	15.40	12.00
1000-grain weight (g)	24.00	19.50
Grain yield (t/ha)	1.8	2.3
Kernel color	White	White
Grain shape	Short bold	Long slender

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

TM8602, a new upland rice

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Several breeding lines were evaluated for yield potential coupled with drought tolerance. TM8602, a derivative of CO 31/C22, was found to be promising.

TM8602 is medium-duration (140 d) and is well adapted to local environmental conditions. In yield trials in 1985-88 wet seasons (Aug seeding), TM8602 averaged 2.2 t/ha, 22.2% higher than local check CO 31 (see table).

TM8602 is intermediate in height with moderate tillering and short bold grain. It performed well under drought conditions, and has been recommended for the upland areas of Tamil Nadu. □

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Performance of TM8602 under drought stress. Tamil Nadu, India.

Season	TM8602				CO 31			
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Drought score ^a		Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Drought score ^a	
			DRT	DRR			DRT	DRR
Wet 1985	135	1.7	1	1	145	1.5	3	3
Wet 1987	145	2.2	1	1	145	2.1	3	3
Wet 1988	130	2.8	1	1	135	1.8	3	3
Mean	137	2.2	1	1	142	1.8	3	3

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice, June 1988. DRT = drought tolerance, DRR = drought recovery.

Seed technology

Effect of wet and dry heat treatment on rice seed germination and seedling vigor

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Hot water and dry heat treatments commonly are used to control a number of seedborne pathogens (fungi, nematodes, and bacteria) and to break

seed dormancy in rice. But these treatments could adversely affect seed vigor and viability.

In international programs involving seed exchange, such as the International Network for Genetic Enhancement of Rice (INGER), a gap of 2-3 mo can occur between treatment and sowing, due to transit and postentry handling operations in recipient countries.